

Supplementary materials for: T. A. Klausen, E. Vlachos, and J. Jørgensen: "A Soft Social Robot to Alleviate Anxiety Symptoms in Children"

1 Fabrication

To make the soft robot, several components were designed and fabricated. These novel components include 3D-printed casting molds, a 3D-printed inner skeleton, a mechanical ear actuation mechanism, and an electronics board. All components were designed using Autodesk Fusion 360. A total of +50 different parts were 3D-printed. Three parts of the ear mechanism were laser-cut in aluminum. The robot was manually assembled and wired.

1.1 Ear mechanism

A mechanism designed and fabricated to actuate the ears of the robot. A simple robot gripper¹ with two arms actuated by a single gear in the middle was used as inspiration. The designed ear mechanism consists of two modified spur gears with a rack and pinion gear in the middle. The rack and pinion gear is connected to a smaller spur gear mounted on the servo motor. A gear ratio of 2:1 between the servo motor gear and the rack and pinion was chosen for more precise actuation of the ears. From the resting position shown in figure 1 the ears can move ~ 10 mm outward and ~ 18 mm inward, measured at the tip of the ear mechanism. This gives a full range of motion (ROM) of ~ 28 mm. The modified spur gear and the rack and pinion were laser cut from 3 mm aluminum, while the servo spur gear was laser cut from 4 mm aluminum. The gear rests and the servo motor mount is 3D-printed and installed directly onto the head insert, as shown in figure 1, during the head casting, further explained in section 1.2.

Figure 1: Ear mechanism mounted on the head insert.

¹Aluminium Robot Gripper <https://www.jsumo.com/aluminum-gripper-robotic-kit> (accessed July 2, 2024)

1.2 Casting workflow

The casting of the robot is done in multiple steps. This process is similar to prior work [1]. The casting process is explained in detail below. In this section, color coding is applied to the technical drawings to distinguish between the different parts.

- **Dark Purple** is used for the casting mold itself.
- **Green** is used for the removable inner parts creating room for chambers.
- **Pink** is used for 3D-printed parts that are integrated into the silicone of the robot.
- **Grey** is mechanical parts implemented during the casting process.
- **Yellow** is air tubes.
- **Blue** is cured silicone.
- **Orange** is cured silicone with fabric inside.
- **Red** is silicone adhesive.

Eco-Flex 00-50 silicone dyed with Silc Pig - Blue (PMS 2757C) was used. The cure times are specified throughout the workflow. Before casting, all silicone was degassed in a vacuum chamber at -0.9 bar for 5 minutes to remove air bubbles.

The first step of the casting process is to make the lower torso of the robot, including the two arms. Firstly, a spacer plate is screwed in place on top of the torso mold. This spacer plate has mounting holes for the three 3D-printed inner parts inserted and screwed into place to create the chest chamber, stomach chamber, and tail-mount chamber (see figure 12). Approximately 310g of silicone is poured into the mold so it covers the chest and stomach chambers by a small amount. The silicone is cured for 24 hours.

Figure 2: Casting the bottom part of the lower torso

When the silicone has cured, the 3D-printed parts for the chest and stomach chamber can be removed. The 3D-printed part for the tail-mount chambers is not removed. When removing the inserts, applying pressurized air between the cured silicone and the inserts

was found to be beneficial, as this will loosen the inserts from the silicone and make them pop out. Once the inserts have been removed, cured silicone rectangular plates with fabric inside are placed on top of the holes to seal the chambers. The silicone adhesive Sil-Poxy is applied around the rectangular plates for complete sealing (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Closing the air chambers

The same procedure described above is used to complete the casting of the lower torso and arms. Approximately 450 g of silicone is poured into the mold to complete the casting of the torso and arms. The silicone is poured until the bottom part of the two spacer plates is reached (see figure 4). After 24 hours of curing, the inner part of the tail-mount chamber and the electronics bed can be removed (see figure 5). A small hole is made through the silicone and rectangular fabric plates in the center of each of the two breathing chambers. An air supply tube is installed (length 40 cm) in each of the holes using silicone adhesive.

Figure 4: Installing the tail-mount and electronics bed placeholder. Casting the remaining part of the torso and arms.

Figure 5: Removing tail-mount and electronics bed placeholder. Installing tubes with silicone adhesive.

The next step is to cast the head unto the torso. As the ears create an undercut in the head mold, they will be cast before mounting the head mold to the lower torso mold. The head insert and holder is screwed into place on the head mold. The spur gears for controlling the two ears in the ears mechanism, see section 1.1, are aligned in the middle of the ears of the head mold. Approximately 12 g of silicone is poured into each of the ears, stopping before overflow (see figure 6). The silicone is left to cure for 4 hours.

Figure 6: Aligning ear mechanism into the head mold. Casting the ears.

The head mold is screwed in place on the torso mold, and the combined mold is placed such that the nose of the robot points downwards. Two air tubes (length 80 cm) for the nostrils of the robot are inserted into the head insert and pressed through until they reach the inner surface of the head mold. Approximately 160 g of silicone is poured into the head mold until the uncured silicone reaches the top of the head insert. The silicone is left to cure for 24 hours. After curing, the holder for the head insert can be removed (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Casting the lower head part. Removing the head insert holder after curing.

The remaining parts of the ear mechanism is installed on the head insert and the inner head filler molds are placed on top of the ear mechanism. Masking tape is added to the seams of the head filler molds to minimize silicone leakage. The tubing should run through the designed guidance to ensure it from getting caught in the ear mechanism. Approximately 170 g of silicone is poured into the head mold until the silicone reaches the top of the mold (see figure 8). It is important not to overflow the silicone into the ear mechanism. The silicone is left to cure for 24 hours. The head filler molds are left inside the robot, as these are removed through the robot's tail opening after the casting process is done. The tubing for the nostrils and the wire for the servo motor are wrapped up and placed inside the head filler molds.

Figure 8: Installing the ear mechanism. Casting the upper head part.

The next step is to cast the back of the robot onto the head and torso to complete the entire casting of the robot. The inner placeholders consist of 8 different 3D-printed parts,

which will create the room inside the robot for the skeleton and electronics bed. These are installed into the free space in the silicone. Adding masking tape to the seams of the inner placeholders is beneficial to minimize silicone leakage. All the parts are designed to be removed throughout the robot’s tail opening after casting. The tubing from the chest and stomach chambers can be placed inside the placeholders while casting the final part. The back mold are screwed into place and clamps are added on the outside of the mold to ensure tight contact (see figure 9). Approximately 320 g of silicone is poured slowly into the hole at the back mold’s top, staying within the pot life of the silicone (18 minutes for Eco-Flex 00-50). The silicone should completely set before leaving it to cure to avoid the need for refilling. The silicone is left to cure for 24 hours.

Figure 9: Installing the inner placeholders. Placing the back mold and casting the back of the robot.

After curing, the three outer molds are carefully separated. Using pressurized air to help loosen the robot from the mold. When the robot is free from the mold, the excess silicone is cut and removed from the top of the head. The inner placeholders and head filler mold are removed through the robot’s tail opening.

The final step is to cast the tail of the robot. The screw insert placeholder is mounted in the tail mold and approximately 70g of silicone is poured until it reaches the top of the mold. The tail cures for 5 hours. After curing, the screw insert placeholder are removed and the screw insert and two M4x10mm bolts (see figure 10) are installed. The tail is mounted to the robot’s body. Two brown glass eyes (20 mm in diameter) (supplier Panduro²), are mounted on the head. Finally, the robot is covered in a thin layer of talcum powder(supplier Matas |) to give a nice feel to the robot’s skin and to minimize the amount of dust that sticks to it. The finalized robot is shown in figure 11.

²Panduro | Brown eyes www.panduro.com (accessed May 14, 2023)

Figure 10: Casting the robot's tail. Installing the screw mount.

Figure 11: Finalized robot

1.3 Skeleton

An internal skeleton was made to mount the electronic components inside the robot. In addition, the skeleton stabilizes the silicone and secures the robot from collapsing under use. The skeleton comprises eight individual 3D-printed parts, all fabricated to be installed through the tail opening after the robot is cast. It is designed to be installed in layers starting by inserting the two back plates (see figure 12a). The robot is kept upside-down when installing the inner skeleton. The back plates ensure that no internal parts or wiring will be caught in the ear mechanism. After this, the top of the skeleton is installed in the robot. The two top parts have an LED light and a concave indent for the silicone cast pressure chamber (see figure 12b). Followed by this, the middle layer of the skeleton is installed. The left side of the skeleton's middle layer keeps the electronics board in place, while the right side has the gyroscope/accelerometer and pressure sensor mounted (see figure 12c). Lastly, the skeleton's bottom layer is installed, which keeps the battery, pumps, and valves in place (see figure 12d). During the skeleton installation, all wires and air tubes are made long enough to be connected on the outside of the robot and put inside afterwards.

Figure 12: Inner skeleton layers

1.4 Code

The Arduino Pro Mini microcontroller's code was written in the Arduino IDE.

The code is centered around the robot's orientation, and three modes are defined based on this: Idle mode; Relief mode; and, Scared mode. The orientation is read from the IMU, where the accelerometer data is used. The pressure sensor initializes with a pressure value from the pressure chamber at startup. For the pressure sensor to count as activated, the pressure must rise to two times the initialized value.

The robot is in Idle mode when placed flat on its belly. In Idle mode, the LEDs pulsate at the breathing rate of the robot. If the pressure sensor on the back of the robot is pressurized during Idle mode, the robot will wiggle its ears from the inward position to the outward position two times, over the duration of six seconds. The robot is in Relief mode when held in an upright position. In this upright position, the LEDs will turn off, and the robot will wait to be hugged. The breathing cycle starts by hugging the robot and thereby applying pressure to the pressure sensor. The robot is in Scared mode when held upside down. In this position, the LEDs will start blinking fast at a rate of 2.5 times per second.

1.5 Software and Hardware

Pumps, valves and a servo motor was used to actuate the robot. A pressure sensor and a gyroscope was used as sensor inputs for the robot. LED lights inside the robot was used for signaling. The parts used for the robot are listed below:

- Pump: MR370BPM 6.0V DC. Manufacturer: NONO1688 (<http://www.nono1688.cn/>)
- Valve: FA0520D 6.0V DC. Manufacturer: ZQDZC (<http://zqdzc.com/>)
- Servo Motor: HS-40 NANO Servo 6.0V DC. Manufacturer: HITEC (<https://hitecred.com/>)
- LED Light: NSPW510DS 3.2V DC. Manufacturer: Nichia (<https://www.nichia.co.jp/en/>)
- Air Pressure Sensor: P/N1139 5.0V DC. Manufacturer: Phidgets (<https://www.phidgets.com/>)
- Gyroscope + Accelerometer: MPU-6050 5.0V DC. Manufacturer: TDK InverseSense (<https://invensense.tdk.com/>)
- Adjustable Step-Down Voltage Regulator: LM2596 DC-DC. Manufacturer: Texas-Instruments (<https://www.ti.com/>)
- Motor Driver: L293D 5.0V DC. Manufacturer: STMicroelectronics (<https://www.st.com/>)
- Battery pack: TigerPower 3S LiPo 11.1V DC 2200 mAh battery pack.
- Arduino Pro Mini

The software and its usage for the project is listed below:

- Arduino IDE: Used for programming the Arduino Mini Pro
- Autodesk Fusion 360: 3D-modelling of casting molds and mechanical parts.
- UltiMaker Cura: Slicing program used for 3D-printing.
- Microsoft Whiteboard: Used for sketching robot designs.

References

- [1] T.A. Klausen et al. “Signalling Emotions with a Breathing Soft Robot”. In: *IEEE Int. Conf. Soft Robot., RoboSoft*. Journal Abbreviation: IEEE Int. Conf. Soft Robot., RoboSoft. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2022, pp. 194–200. ISBN: 9781665408288 (ISBN). DOI: 10.1109/RoboSoft54090.2022.9762140.